

Polarographic Behaviour of Carbohydrates: Part II. Kinetics of the Mutarotation of Maltose

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The kinetics of the mutarotation of β -maltose have been studied polarographically using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as the supporting electrolyte. By adopting the following scheme of mutarotation equilibria; β -maltose $\rightleftharpoons \nu \rightleftharpoons \alpha$ -maltose, where ν denotes the reducible free aldehyde form of maltose, the values of the four rate constants of the mutarotation process and the concentration of the free aldehyde form of maltose at equilibrium were calculated.

THE mutarotation of freshly prepared aqueous solutions of aldoses and ketoses involves the establishment of equilibrium between the two diastereomeric cyclic hemiacetals. Kinetics of the mutarotation of aldoses such as glucose, xylose, maltose etc. have been studied by several workers¹⁻³ polarimetrically. But earlier workers determined the values of the rate constants of the mutarotation adopting the following scheme :

The above scheme seems unlikely to be exact because the chemical behaviour of aldoses such as the formation of oximes, osazones etc. suggests the formation of reactive free aldehyde form in the system⁴⁻⁵.

Since aldoses give small polarographic reduction wave the limiting current of which is kinetic in nature and which is governed by the formation of reducible γ -form from both α - and β -aldose it offers the possibility of studying the kinetics of the mutarotation of aldoses by the polarographic method⁶⁻⁹. Results of such an investigation on maltose will be reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Apparatus : A general purpose Cambridge Polarograph in conjunction with a Cambridge spot galvanometer was used for polarographic measurements. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics : $m = 1.79\text{mg/sec}$, $t = 2.90\text{ sec}$. in distilled water at a mercury reservoir height of 66 cm.

Method : After preliminary adjustments the potential of the DME was set at $-1.58\text{ volts vs. SCE}$

which was well on the plateau of the polarographic wave of maltose and the first galvanometer reading was noted 2 min after the addition of maltose to the deoxygenated phosphate buffer in the electrolysis cell placed in a water thermostat set at 30° . The moment at which maltose was added to the buffer was taken as the "Zero time". Galvanometer readings were then noted after every two minutes till the attainment of equilibrium.

Concentrations of α - and β - form of maltose at equilibrium were determined polarimetrically using a Bellingham and Stanley Polarimeter.

Results and Discussion

The limiting current vs. time curve shows that the limiting current decreases gradually with time. After about 40 min the current attains a constant value and no further decrease in the galvanometer deflection is observed indicating that equilibrium has been attained.

Los *et al*^{7,8} showed that the kinetic current for the reduction of γ -form corresponding to the reaction scheme shown in Table 1 may be expressed as a function of x_∞ and t .

TABLE 1. RATE CONSTANTS OF THE MUTAROTATION OF β -MALTOS E IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER (pH 6.8)

Mutarotation scheme : $\beta\text{-maltose} \xrightleftharpoons[k_1']{k_1} \gamma \xrightleftharpoons[k_2']{k_2} \alpha\text{-maltose}$			
Forward rate constant		Backward rate constant	
$k_1(\text{sec}^{-1})$	$k_2(\text{sec}^{-1})$	$k_1'(\text{sec}^{-1})$	$k_2'(\text{sec}^{-1})$
34.58.10 ⁻⁴	5.62.10 ⁻⁴	18.25	3.22

$$i_k(t) = 2F10^{-3} \bar{q} \sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{k_1' + k_2'} \right)} [k_1 a - (k_1 - k_2)x + (k_1 - k_2) x_\infty e^{-kt}] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

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Where a is the total aldose concentration, x_∞ is the concentration of the γ -form at equilibrium, and D is the diffusion coefficient.

By subtracting the corresponding equation for time t' , where $t' - t = \Delta > 0$ from equation (2) and after further simplification the following equation is obtained :

$$\ln[i_{k(t)} - i_{k(t')}] = \ln 2F \cdot 10^{-3} \bar{q} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{k_1 - k_2}{(k_1' + k_2')^{\frac{1}{2}}} x_\infty (1 - e^{k\Delta}) - kt \quad \dots (3)$$

The plot of $\ln[i_{k(t)} - i_{k(t')}]$ against t at constant Δ yields a straight line with slope k which is related to the four rate constants by the equation,

$$k = \frac{k_1 k_2' + k_1' k_2}{k_1' + k_2'} \quad \dots (4)$$

and an intercept on the ordinate :

$$\ln 2F \cdot 10^{-3} \bar{q} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{k_1 - k_2}{(k_1' + k_2')^{\frac{1}{2}}} x_\infty (1 - e^{k\Delta}) \quad \dots (5)$$

At equilibrium, i.e. when $t = \infty$, equation (2) becomes

$$ik_{(\infty)} = 2F \cdot 10^{-3} \bar{q} \sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{k_1' + k_2'} \right)} [k_1 a - (k_1 - k_2) x_\infty] \quad (6)$$

The equilibrium constant for the overall process

is given by

$$\alpha\text{-form} \rightleftharpoons \beta\text{-form}$$

$$\frac{x_\infty}{a - x_\infty} = \frac{k_1 k_2'}{k_1' k_2} = K \quad \dots (7)$$

The slope and the intercept with the ordinate of $\log [ik_{(t)} - ik_{(\infty)}]$ vs. t curve (Fig. 2) were calculated and found to be $-4.33 \cdot 10^{-4} \mu A/\text{sec.}$ and $0.17 \mu A$ respectively.

Using these values and equation (4), (5), (6) and (7) the values of the rate constants of mutarotation of maltose were calculated and shown in table 1.

The equilibrium concentration of the free aldehyde form of maltose was calculated with these values and found to be $9.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ moles/lit. which is about 0.009% of the total maltose concentration.

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References

1. H. S. ISBELL. *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1937, **18**, 505.
2. H. S. ISBELL and W. W. PIGMAN, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1937; **18**, 141.
3. C. N. RILBER and N. A. SORENSSEN, *Kgl. Norske Videnskabs Selskabs Skrifter*, 1938, No. 1.
4. J. W. HAAS, D. D. STOREY and J. LYNCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 145.
5. J. W. HAAS and R. E. KADUNCE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4910.
6. P. DELAHAY and J. E. STRASSNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 893.
7. J. M. LOS and K. WIESNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6346.
8. J. M. LOS, L. B. SIMPSON and K. WIESNER. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1564.
9. T. IKEDA and M. SENDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1973, **46**, 2107.
10. F. H. CHOWDHURY, N. B. FOZDER and S. A. TARAFDAR. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1139.